

Enhancing Outcome in Class I Composite Restoration: Custom Shield and Occlusal Stamp

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ABSTRACT

Background: Bio-mimetic dentistry refers to techniques that replicate the natural structure and function of teeth. Restoring cavities that affect the buccal, palatal, or lingual cusps can be challenging, especially when using direct composite restorations, as accurately recreating the cusps' height and shape freehand is often difficult. With this approach, the shape and height of the cusp are first captured before any reduction occurs, using a silicone index and an occlusal surface stamp technique. This index allows for the precise recreation of the cusp's original form after the reduction process.

Case Presentation: A 32-year-old female patient presented with sensitivity in the lower right posterior region. Upon clinical examination, a Class I caries with buccal extension was observed on tooth 47. A small amount of putty was placed on the buccal and occlusal surfaces to form a custom shield. The occlusal surface was then recorded using a microbrush and flowable composite to create an occlusal stamp. After preparing the cavity, the standard etching and bonding procedures were followed. The buccal wall was restored using the shield, and the cavity was filled incrementally. The occlusal restoration was shaped with the help of the previously created stamp. Finally, finishing and polishing were done using discs.

Conclusion: This case report demonstrates the effectiveness of the 'Custom Shield as a matrix along with the occlusal stamp technique.' This combined approach offers both esthetic and functional advantages, ensuring predictable, high-quality restorations.

Key words: Custom shield technique, Composite resin, Conservative dentistry, Esthetics, 3-D layering technique, Incremental layering.

INTRODUCTION

The term "bio" in Greek signifies life, and "mimesis" refers to imitation. In the context of dentistry, bio-mimetic principles focus on restoring lost dental tissues with materials that not only restore full functionality but also withstand functional stresses while maintaining aesthetic outcomes. This is the fundamental concept of biomimetic dentistry.¹ Today, the field of dentistry faces an increasing demand for aesthetic standards, which extends even to the posterior region of the mouth. One technique that addresses this need is the polychromatic layering method, also known as 3D layering. This technique utilizes various shades—opaque, body, and translucent— to create highly aesthetic direct restorations.²

Occlusal surfaces of posterior teeth are particularly vulnerable to caries.³ Additionally, the buccal surfaces of mandibular teeth and the palatal surfaces of maxillary teeth are also commonly affected. Despite a decline in the overall incidence of tooth decay, dentin carious lesions, often referred to as "Hidden Caries," are still frequently encountered.^{2,4} These lesions are typically not visible on the surface, as the occlusal enamel remains intact. However, underlying decay can be detected by a bluish or black discoloration beneath the enamel.⁵

Different matrices, whether for metallic or non-metallic restorations, are primarily designed to help establish the contour and contact of the proximal surfaces. However, they do not assist in achieving accurate occlusion or mesio-distal contours.⁶ The shaping of occlusal and smooth surfaces relies on the skill and dexterity of the dentist, which carries the risk of over-finishing or under-finishing, leading to surfaces that are either over- or under-restored.⁷

To overcome challenges in Compound Class I cases, Gaetano Paolone, Salvatore Scolavino, and the Style Italiano team introduced a new method for placing composite restorations, called the "Custom Shield" technique.⁸ Before starting cavity preparation, a custom putty index is created to capture the buccal and palatal contours of the posterior teeth. This index is then used to replicate the original anatomical shape of the buccal and palatal surfaces. This case report explores a novel biomimetic approach for restoring Class I compound lesions, integrating the custom shield technique with the occlusal stamp method.

CASE REPORT

A 32-year-old female patient, in good health, presented with a primary complaint of mild cold sensitivity in the lower right posterior tooth region. Upon clinical examination, a Class I cavity with buccal extension was observed on tooth 47 (A). The presence of a blackish hue under the buccal cusps suggested that decay removal would likely result in the loss of the buccal cusps. To prevent damage during this process, a custom shield was created by applying a small amount of putty material on both

the buccal and occlusal surfaces (B). The occlusal stamp was recorded using a microbrush and flowable composite resin (Palfique Estelite Flow Quick) (C). Cavity preparation involved the use of a spherical diamond drill at high speed. For the removal of infected dentin, spoon excavators and carbide burs were utilized. After eliminating the decay, caries removal dye (BRIX3000) was applied to ensure that no carious tissue remained, followed by further debridement if necessary (D). The cavity was thoroughly rinsed, and pulp protection was applied using Calcimol LC. Selective enamel etching was carried out with 37% phosphoric acid (D-Tech), followed by rinsing with distilled water for one minute (E). The universal bonding agent (Palfique Universal Bond) was then applied to the enamel and dentinal walls of the cavity using an applicator tip for 20 seconds (F). A thin layer of enamel shade composite (Palfique Estelite) was placed on the custom shield and adapted to the tooth, with curing light directed through the cavity to the shield's inner surface (G). After curing, the buccal anatomy was reconstructed. At this stage, a rubber dam was applied (H). Incremental layering of nanohybrid resin composite was performed in the occlusal cavity, starting with a body shade layer, followed by light curing for 20 seconds. Application of tints was then completed, with the final top layer of enamel shade applied. A PTFE (Polytetrafluoroethylene) tape was positioned over the final increment, followed by precise placement of the occlusal stamp using gentle digital pressure (I). Another round of curing was done for 20 seconds. After removing the stamp, occlusion was checked using Shofu Super Snap Rainbow Kit, progressing from coarse to fine disks for finishing and polishing. Finally, articulating papers with thicknesses of 80 and 15 microns were used to check the occlusion through the progressive color transfer method, while finishing diamond burs helped to refine the necessary areas (J).

DISCUSSION

Biomimetic dentistry has revolutionized restorative procedures by focusing on achieving function, aesthetics, and durability. A key aspect of this approach is the use of composite restorations, which offer the benefits of minimally invasive techniques, and in some cases, no preparation at all. This has given rise to the concept of Bio-Esthetics, where aesthetic outcomes are increasingly attainable with both refined traditional methods and the development of innovative techniques. However, the process of creating high-quality direct composite restorations remains challenging, requiring a significant level of experience, skill, and precision to successfully replicate the natural form and function of the tooth.⁹

While direct composite restorations offer a conservative, patient-friendly alternative to more invasive treatments, they are not without challenges. In contrast, indirect restorations—typically fabricated in a laboratory—offer more controlled outcomes in terms of contact, contour, and occlusion. These restorations benefit from the expertise of laboratory technicians, which allows for precise

adjustments before final placement. However, the main drawback of indirect restorations is the longer procedure time and potential for higher patient cost due to the need for multiple visits.

Direct restorations, on the other hand, allow for a quicker, more efficient procedure, especially in high-volume practices. However, they require the clinician to be highly skilled in managing the restorative process, particularly when recreating the complex anatomy of the tooth. The handcrafting of occlusion and form, especially in areas like cusps and fossae, presents more challenges in direct restorations than in indirect ones, where these factors are controlled in the lab.⁶

The custom shield technique for direct composite restorations, as described here, offers a practical solution to some of these challenges, particularly in Class I cavities. The advantage of using this method is the replication of the original buccal/palatal anatomy which does not necessitate many corrections. There is a decrease in the time required for finishing and polishing the restoration. The benefit of a putty index is that the precise buccal/palatal/lingual contour and shape can be acquired. Putty index perfectly defines the sagittal dimensions, the length, and the cuspal position of the desired final restoration and labial or palatal curvature of the restoration.^{10,11}

The stamp acts as a guide to shape the occlusal anatomy during the final increment of composite application, which is less time-consuming than traditional finishing and polishing methods. When compared to traditional direct restorations, the stamp technique reduces the risk of under- or over-contouring, leading to a more predictable and stable result. In this case, the stamp technique's primary benefit lies in its ability to recreate an accurate cusp-fossa relationship with minimal finishing time, which is essential for high-quality restorations. This makes the technique particularly valuable in practices where efficiency is critical, without compromising on aesthetic or functional outcomes. Additionally, the incremental application of composite, combined with the use of the stamp matrix, reduces porosity in the final restoration—addressing one of the major challenges of direct composite procedures. By minimizing oxygen interference during polymerization, this approach not only enhances the quality of the restoration but also improves its long-term durability.¹¹

Another key benefit is the simplicity and speed of the process. By reducing the amount of finishing and polishing required, the stamp technique offers a significant time-saving advantage, especially in practices dealing with a high volume of patients. The accuracy and efficiency of this approach provide clinicians with a reliable method for achieving excellent functional and aesthetic outcomes, even under time constraints.^{11,12}

Despite its advantages, the stamp technique is not without limitations. One of the main drawbacks is the high level of skill and expertise required to execute it accurately. The placement of the occlusal stamp must be precise to achieve the desired cusp-fossa relationship. If the stamp is positioned incorrectly, the final restoration may not replicate the natural tooth anatomy, potentially leading to

functional issues such as premature occlusal contacts, wear, or misalignment with the opposing dentition. This places a significant demand on the clinician's proficiency, making it less suitable for less experienced practitioners or those unfamiliar with this technique.

Furthermore, while the stamp technique minimizes finishing time, it still requires careful attention to detail during composite application and placement. Although the incremental technique reduces porosity and improves the overall quality of the restoration, there is still potential for minor imperfections that could affect the longevity and function of the restoration over time. Future research could focus on refining the technique further to minimize the impact of these challenges, perhaps by exploring ways to standardize the occlusal stamp placement for more consistent results.

Another potential area for improvement is the scalability of the technique in different clinical settings. While the stamp method is efficient and effective in high-volume practices, its reliance on a skilled operator may limit its applicability in settings with less experienced clinicians. Further training and development of simplified, standardized tools could enhance its usability and expand its application.¹³

The stamp technique for direct composite restorations offers significant advantages in terms of functional, aesthetic, and time-related benefits, especially when treating Class I cavities. Its ability to recreate accurate occlusal anatomy with minimal finishing makes it a valuable tool in high-volume dental practices. However, the technique's reliance on precise application and a high level of skill places demands on the clinician, making it essential for practitioners to have substantial expertise in order to achieve optimal results.⁵ Although challenges remain in the areas of training and standardization, the technique shows promise for improving the quality and efficiency of direct composite restorations in clinical practice. Future studies and innovations in the technique could further address these limitations and help refine the approach for broader use.

CONCLUSION

The custom shield and stamp technique provided an innovative solution to the challenges presented by the unconventional cavity in this case. By accurately replicating the natural tooth topography, this method not only ensured superior marginal adaptation and anatomical contour but also minimized the risk of overhangs or voids, which are common in traditional free-hand restorations. The operator's proficiency with this technique was crucial in overcoming the cavity's unique anatomy, leading to a durable and aesthetically pleasing outcome.

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FIGURES

FIGURE 1: A - Pre-Operative Photograph, B - Fabrication of silicone putty index, C - Fabrication of occlusal stamp, D - Cavity preparation after caries removal, E - Acid Etching

FIGURE 2: F - Application of bonding agent, G - Placement of putty index, H - Fabrication of buccal composite wall and application of rubber dam, I - Placement of Occlusal stamp after PTFE tape, J - Post-Operative Photograph.

